

The socio-psychological factors influencing integration: What does the literature say?

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The success of refugee integration relies on a wide range of policies and underlying factors. Amongst these are socio-psychological factors both within and between groups of refugees and receiving communities. Understanding these factors can play a significant role in more effective programme design and practice of integration.

Over an extended period a significant body of research has developed concerning these factors. In order to make this work more accessible, and to provide a foundation for new research being undertaken by the FOCUS consortium, a systematic review of published research was undertaken. The findings presented in summary form here suggest a number of distinct factors as linked to the socio-psychological integration.

Background Concepts

Different groups and individuals may have significantly different understanding of what they mean when they use concepts such as integration. As such, it is important to be clear about core definitions and to reflect the substantial work which has been done to developing a shared understanding in this field.

Integration is here defined as a dynamic two-way interaction process between refugees and members of the receiving communities. It is a complex process which always involves interaction at several levels between groups of newcomers and members of the receiving communities. This involves a number of core dimensions: rights and citizenship, language and cultural knowledge, safety and stability, social connections, and structural aspects of integration (employment, housing, education and health)[1].

Figure 1: Four hierarchical dimensions of integration as defined by Ager and Strang (2008)

Socio-psychological integration refers to between-group relations such as attitudes, mutual group perceptions and tensions, behavioural intentions, frequency and valence of contact etc. Migration inevitably results in societal changes in both groups and these changes are indicated by relations that the refugees and members of the receiving communities have with each other. While here are some overlaps between these factors and the more extensively researched socio-economic dimensions of integration, they are distinct and clearly influence each other.

The process of socio-psychological integration has been a topic of many research papers as well as reports from practice of working with refugees. As a part of the FOCUS project, a literature review on findings in these publications was conducted for a period until January 2019.

[1] Ager, A. & Strang, A. (2008). Understanding Integration: A conceptual framework, *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 21 (2), pp. 166–191.

Systematic Literature Review: method and key questions

A **systematic literature review** is an extensive process which follows precise methodology and pre-defined steps in order to answer research questions of interest. The purpose is to ensure that all relevant literature has been found and properly analysed, and that conclusions drawn from the findings are strong and valid. This methodology follows a strict procedure[2]:

- » Relevant data bases are identified
- » Key search words and phrases are defined
- » Key words and phrases are then searched for in the databases and all relevant studies are identified
- » Relevant studies are reviewed in several iterations and only the ones complying with pre-defined quality criteria are retained for analysis
- » Analysis of the final collection of studies is conducted
- » Findings are summarized and presented in a report

Around 10 000 publications were found by searching for key terms in four major databases, and after reviewing their titles and abstracts, 692 were retained as relevant. Out of these, 74 were doubles found in more than on database.

In total, 618 unique publications were identified in the four databases and eight additional articles were retrieved from other sources. After the second round of review, 147 publications were kept for further analysis.

The third and final review iteration yielded 87 publications for the final collection of studies that were subjected to content analysis of findings on socio-psychological integration of migrants and receiving communities.

All of these publications were then analysed in detail regarding their research questions, methodology used and results.

The two research questions guiding this literature review:

- » What are the factors and indicators of socio-psychological integration of refugees and receiving communities?
- » What are the impact factors of refugee migration on the receiving communities?

Key findings

The detailed review of the literature showed several concepts as key for socio-psychological integration of refugees and members of the receiving communities (Table 1):

[2] Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) available at: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

Thoughts	Perceptions	Behaviour & behav.l intentions	Other
Understanding integration	Refugees' perceptions of discrimination and attitudes of the receiving communities	Contact between members of the two groups	Emotions and solidarity
Refugee's return wishes	Attitudes	Social distance	Political & national orientations
	Inter-group threat		
Support for rights & asylum policies	Perception of form of acculturation process	Behavioural intentions	Interventions aimed to change negative attitudes
	Perceptions of distinctive migrant groups		

Table 1: Key concepts of socio-psychological integration of refugees and members of the receiving communities

In the research literature some concepts were more frequent than others – indicating their relatively higher scientific importance and potential for being addressed in integration practices. They were also closely related to the overarching concept of socio-psychological integration and are relevant for the new research elements of the FOCUS project. These concepts are: understanding of integration, attitudes towards refugees, inter-group threat, perception of form of acculturation process, inter-group contact, social distance, support for rights and asylum policies, behavioural intentions and refugee perceptions of discrimination. Other concepts that were studied are refugees' return wishes, perceptions of distinctive migrant groups, emotions and solidarity, political and national orientations and interventions aimed to change negative attitudes. Findings from these studies will be briefly described.

Understanding integration

The systematic review revealed that when asked about opinions on integration, members of the receiving society and refugees report similar views on what integration is[3]. It was seen as *a three-point continuum* with expectations of interaction held for each point. These points are:

Figure 3 Understanding of what integration is from Ager & Strang (2004)

“**No trouble**” stands for peaceful coexistence, but without the intention to interact between the groups.

“**Mixing**” was mentioned more often by the participants and represents the acceptance of differences and diversity, friendliness and participation in shared activities.

“**Belonging**” is the highest state of interaction which includes positive thoughts, emotions and behaviours in the interactions between the groups and is much more than their mere coexistence.

[3] Ager, A., & Strang, A. (2004). The experience of integration: A qualitative study of refugee integration in the local communities of Pollokshaws and Islington. Home Office Online Report 55/04. London: Home Office.

These views of characteristics of an “integrated community” are shared between refugees and the members of the receiving communities which is an important starting point in the process of their integration.

Both groups report key issues which, when resolved, contribute to the process of integration. These key issues are: safety and stability, skills in the language of the receiving communities, guidance on administration and services, between-group cultural understanding, education, employment and housing.

Language is perceived as a bridge in forming positive relations between groups and of great importance for communication with institutions, services and shared activities. It was also seen as an important factor of well-being, education, access to labour market and feeling of belonging in refugees.

Attitudes

Attitudes are not only related to the way we think about relevant others, but also to the way we feel and behave (or plan to behave) towards them, making attitudes highly influential in building and maintaining relationships between refugees and members of the receiving communities. Attitudes towards refugees were studied in relation to other constructs such as perception of threat, quality and quantity of contact, intergroup emotions and empathy and political affiliations and ideologies.

From the pool of research on attitudes of members of the receiving communities, conclusions can be drawn about people who have more negative attitudes towards migrants: males, older participants, less educated, those who believe their opinion is supported by the general public, who hold false beliefs regarding the migrants, nation glorifiers and politically right-wing oriented individuals.

It was found that the way members of the receiving communities **think** about asylum seekers (their **beliefs**, as opposed to how they **feel**) is most effective in influencing overall attitudes towards asylum seekers[4][5].

Interventions aimed to change negative attitudes

Several intervention studies aimed at improving negative attitudes of members of the receiving communities towards refugees and asylum seekers. General findings suggest that interventions which used

What is viewed as an “integrated community”?

•Feeling safe from threats posed by other people

•Tolerance

•Welcoming climate

•Friendliness

•Belonging and feeling part of the community

•Having friends

•For refugees: opportunity to do the same things and go to the same places as other people

[4] Croucamp, C. J., O'Connor, M., Pedersen, A., & Breen, L. J. (2017). Predicting community attitudes towards asylum seekers: A multi-component model. *Australian Journal of Psychology*, 69(4), pp. 237–246.

[5] Pedersen, A., Attwell, J., & Heveli, D. (2005). Prediction of negative attitudes towards Australian asylum seekers: False beliefs, nationalism, and self-esteem. *Australian Journal of Psychology*, 57, pp. 148–160.

contact as an intervention showed success in shifting attitudes towards the positive pole and these findings support the knowledge about the strength of contact between the groups[6][7]. Interventions aimed at changing negative attitudes by providing the participants information about refugees did not prove to be so successful[8][10]. Another study found that providing information to the members of the receiving communities about economic cost of integration reduced pro-social behaviour, even in most religious participants who, in case without such information, donated most[9].

As only one of the reported studies tested the effects of intervention long after it was completed and found no difference between the initial levels of attitudes and 7 weeks after the intervention, there are no clear conclusions on the long-term effects of interventions aiming to change negative attitudes.

Attitudes towards refugees and perceived inter-group threat

Relationship between the perception of threat from and attitudes towards refugees and asylum seekers has been extensively studied and a strong and consistent negative relationship between them is reported in the literature.

Two different but related kinds of threat were often used as predictors of attitudes towards refugees: realistic threat and symbolic threat. Realistic threat refers to how a group sees their economic interests endangered by the interests of the competing group, while symbolic threat is about feelings that own group's values and culture are endangered by the other group. In the context of integration, realistic threat is related to the level of socio-economic integrity, while symbolic threat is associated with the socio-psychological integration. Realistic threat is related to prejudice more strongly than symbolic threat, but their joint influence best predicts negative attitudes towards refugees and prejudice⁵. In other words, people are most likely to be negative towards the group they feel threatened by when they feel both their socio-economic situation and their culture and customs are in danger.

The literature identifies different levels of prejudice and negative perception between different groups within receiving communities[11].

Attitudes towards forms of acculturation

Acculturation is a process that can take up several forms based on whether the two interacting groups preserve elements of their culture (preserve/abandon) and take up elements of the culture of the other group (adopt/reject). **Integration** is a two-way process in which both groups preserve and adapt their original culture and adopt elements of the other culture. In contrast, **assimilation** requires from the newcomer group (or a minority group) to abandon their culture and fully adopt the majority culture, depriving the minority of their customs and ways.

[6] Cameron, L., Rutland, A., & Brown, R. (2007). Promoting children's positive intergroup attitudes towards stigmatized groups: Extended contact and multiple classification skills training. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 31(5), pp. 454–466.

[7] Cameron, L., Rutland, A., Brown, R., & Douch, R. (2006). Changing Children's Intergroup Attitudes Toward Refugees: Testing Different Models of Extended Contact. *Child Development*, 77(5), pp. 1208–1219.

[8] Crowell, T. A. (2000, August). Attitudes toward refugees surviving human rights abuses before and after exposure to refugee-related information. *Dissertation Abstracts International: Section B: The Sciences and Engineering*.

[9] Bansak, K., Hainmueller, J. & Hangartner, D. (2017). Europeans support a proportional allocation of asylum seekers. *Nat. Hum. Behav.* 1, 0133.

[10] Turner, R. N., & Brown, R. (2008). Improving children's attitudes toward refugees: An evaluation of a school-based multicultural curriculum and an anti-racist intervention. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, pp. 38(5), 1295–1328.

[11] Schweitzer, R., Perkoulidis, S., Krome, S., Ludlow, C., & Ryan, M. (2005). Attitudes towards refugees: The dark side of prejudice in Australia. *Australian Journal of Psychology*, 57(3), pp. 170–179.

Support for different types of acculturation is related to attitudes, contact and intergroup threat. Members of the receiving communities who had more positive attitudes towards migrants, experienced more positive contact and felt less threatened, are also more supportive of migrants retaining their culture. They also believe that their own community should show effort to adapt to the migrants[12].

Attitudes and contact between groups

Contact has a powerful influence on relations between members of different groups. It is closely related to all three components of attitudes: *thoughts* people have about each other, *emotions* and *behavioural intentions* towards other people. Research demonstrates that these three components of attitudes are related to quality of contact with the members of the out-group.

Quality of contact was consistently found to be a stronger predictor of attitudes rather than the frequency of contact, which means that the feelings evoked during the contact are on average more important than the quantity of contact. However, *interaction* between the frequency and valence of contact experiences has strongest relationship with desirable outcomes[13].

**Which is more important:
quantity or quality of
intergroup contact?**

The answer is: both. Frequent positive contact between groups is associated with desirable outcomes: positive thoughts, emotions and behaviours in interaction.

Research shows that for positive attitudes it is not only important for refugees to *personally* have positive relations with other groups (direct contact), but also that *other members of their own group* have positive experiences with members of the other group (extended contact)[14]. This finding suggests that the contact the members of one's social network have with other group can influence attitudes at the personal level.

Social distance

Social distance is the unwillingness to engage in different types of relationship with the members of the other group. It is related to negative attitudes and prejudice, right-wing political orientation[15], and perception of inter-group threat. In other words, persons who on average are more negative towards migrants, perceive them as threatening and have more conservative political views, are also more likely to reject migrants and prefer a greater social distance. These findings were regularly reported in research literature linking attitudes, perception of threat and social distance[16][17].

[12] Geschke, D., Mummendey, A., Kessler, T., & Funke, F. (2010). Majority members' acculturation goals as predictors and effects of attitudes and behaviours towards migrants. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 49(3), pp. 489–506.

[13] Barlow, F. K., Paolini, S., Pedersen, A., Hornsey, M. J., Radke, H. R. M., Harwood, J., Sibley, C. G. (2012). The contact caveat: Negative contact predicts increased prejudice more than positive contact predicts reduced prejudice. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 38(12), pp. 1629–1643.

[14] De Tezanos-Pinto, P., Mazziotta, A., & Feuchte, F. (2017). Intergroup contact and reconciliation among Liberian refugees: A multilevel analysis in a multiple groups setting. *Peace and Conflict: Journal of Peace Psychology*, 23(3), pp. 228–238.

[15] Kim, H. J., Yoo, H. Y., & Chung, Y. K. (2015). Social distance towards the North Korean refugees in South Korean society. *Korea Observer*, 46(2), pp. 295–320.

[16] Ajduković, D., Čorkalo Biruški, D., Gregurović, M., Matić Bojić, J., Župarić-Iljić, D. (2019). Challenges of integrating refugees into Croatian society: Attitudes of citizens and the readiness of local communities. Government of the Republic of Croatia. Office for Human Rights and rights of National Minorities.

[17] Bruneau, E., Kteily, N., & Laustsen, L. (2018). The unique effects of blatant dehumanization on attitudes and behavior towards Muslim refugees during the European 'refugee crisis' across four countries. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 48(5), pp. 645–662.

In contrast *less* social distance is perceived towards *assimilated* refugees than integrated ones – probably because the assimilated refugees are perceived as willing to let go their culture and customs[18].

Support for the rights and policies of migrants

Studies suggests that the support for refugees to hold and utilize their rights and support for integrative asylum policies are related to people’s overall humanitarian values and lower perception of threat[19]. Members of the receiving communities are more likely to support the rights of those they perceive as involuntary migrants (refugees) than voluntary migrants (e.g. economic migrants)[20].

Emotions and solidarity

Findings imply that emotions towards refugees are related to the characteristics of respondents and of migrants they are expressing emotions to. Generally, economic migrants induced more negative emotions, while empathy and sympathy were more likely felt towards asylum seekers[21]. Dehumanization as a form of affective-cognitive expression towards the members of the out-group was found to be related to right wing authoritarianism, social dominance orientation and negative emotions, as well as prejudice[22].

Behavioural intentions

Intentions to behave a certain way towards members of another group are commonly referred to as **behavioural intentions**. Research shows that humanitarian views about refugees are related not only to positive thinking about asylum rights, but also to the behavioural intentions, so that receiving community members who are more oriented towards “what is humane” show more support for asylum rights, more positive and less negative behavioural intentions[23]. Behavioural intentions are also linked to the frequency of contact, perception of threat and right-wing political orientation[10].

Studies show that certain groups of people are more prone to showing pro-social behaviour towards migrants: females, younger individuals, those with higher incomes, those who feel closer to refugees and those who feel they are doing better than refugees.

[18] Koc, Y., & Anderson, J. R. (2018). Social distance toward Syrian refugees: The role of intergroup anxiety in facilitating positive relations. *Journal of Social Issues*, 74(4), pp. 790-811.

[19] Hercowitz-Amir, A., Raijman, R., & Davidov, E. (2017). Host or hostile? Attitudes towards asylum seekers in Israel and in Denmark. *International Journal of Comparative Sociology*, 58(5), pp. 416–439.

[20] Verkuyten, M., Mepham, K., & Kros, M. (2018). Public attitudes towards support for migrants: the importance of perceived voluntary and involuntary migration. *Ethnic & Racial Studies*, 41(5), pp. 901–918.

[21] Verkuyten, M. (2004). Emotional reactions to and support for immigrant policies: Attributed responsibilities to categories of asylum seekers. *Social Justice Research*, 17(3), pp. 293–314.

[22] Esses, V. M., Veenvliet, S., Hodson, G., & Mihic, L. (2008). Justice, morality, and the dehumanization of refugees. *Social Justice Research*, 21(1), pp. 4–25.

[23] Yitmen, Ş., & Verkuyten, M. (2018). Positive and negative behavioural intentions towards refugees in Turkey: The roles of national identification, threat, and humanitarian concern. *Journal of community & applied social psychology*, 28(4), pp. 230-243.

Political and national orientations and their effects

Relationship between political orientation and attitudes towards refugees and asylum seekers was frequently studied. The results repeatedly point to conclusion that the more members of the receiving communities lean towards right-wing political parties which promote conservatism and strong national structures and relations, they hold more prejudice towards out-groups and feel more threatened by them. Specific concepts, right-wing authoritarianism (support for the ideals of conservatism and authority) and social dominance orientation (belief that strong hierarchical social order is necessary) were consistently found to predict undesired outcomes: prejudice, negative emotions and behaviours towards refugees and asylum seekers[24][25][26].

Some findings suggest that not only is the political orientation important for relations towards refugees, but also the strength of support for policies linked to belief that the “solution for refugee crisis is simple”[27]. Together with contact quality, findings of studies of these concepts are most robust throughout socio-psychological literature reviewed for the purpose of FOCUS project, showing high stability of effect direction.

Perceptions of distinctive migrant groups

Several studies showed that members of the receiving communities make distinctions between migrant groups and show different attitudes towards them. Refugees induce most positive attitudes and feelings, while economic migrants are most often rejected[28][29]. Asylum seekers and refugees are often viewed indistinctively from each other, but the differences between attitudes and emotions towards these two groups and economic migrants are consistently significant[30]. Some findings imply that the origin (home country, ethnicity) of refugees is also important for the formation of attitudes towards them[24].

[24] Anderson, J. R. (2018). The prejudice against asylum seekers scale: presenting the psychometric properties of a new measure of classical and conditional attitudes. *Journal of Social Psychology*, 158(6), pp. 694–710.

[25] Anderson, J. R., Stuart, A., & Rossen, I. (2015). Not all negative: Macro justice principles predict positive attitudes towards asylum seekers in Australia. *Australian Journal of Psychology*, 67(4), pp. 207–213.

[26] Nickerson, A. M., & Louis, W. R. (2008). Nationality versus humanity? Personality, identity, and norms in relation to attitudes toward asylum seekers. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 38(3), pp. 796–817.

[27] Van Prooijen, J.-W., Krouwel, A. P. M., & Emmer, J. (2018). Ideological responses to the EU refugee crisis: The left, the right, and the extremes. *Social Psychological and Personality Science*, 9(2), pp. 143–150.

[28] Abeywickrama, R. S., Laham, S. M., & Crone, D. L. (2018). Immigration and receiving communities: The utility of threats and emotions in predicting action tendencies toward refugees, asylum-seekers and economic migrants. *Journal of Social Issues*.

[29] DeVaul-Fetters, A. N. (2009). Reactions to refugees: Do stronger believers in a just world compensate, dehumanize, and perceive refugees as more responsible for their status? (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University of Western Ontario, London, Canada.

[30] Kotzur, P. F., Forsbach, N., & Wagner, U. (2017). Choose your words wisely: Stereotypes, emotions, and action tendencies toward fled people as a function of the group label. *Social Psychology*, 48(4), pp. 226–241.

Refugee perception of discrimination

Intergroup discrimination is defined as behaviour by which members of one group deny a right, opportunity or service to members of another group simply because they belong to the out-group, or they favour members of their own group although these individuals may be less qualified or entitled to such a right, opportunity or service. Perception of discrimination is one's personal interpretation of a situation in which she/he felt denied of a right, opportunity or service based on their belonging to a specific group.

Perception of discrimination among refugees was related to a series of outcomes such as increased wishes to return home[31], worse mental health and reduced willingness to maintain relationships with the members of the receiving communities[32]. Negative contact with members of the receiving communities was related to refugees' and migrants' perceptions of discrimination in several studies[32][33].

Personal discrimination ("Me") is negatively related to psychological well-being.
Group discrimination ("Us") is negatively related to the identification with the receiving communities.[34]

Refugees' return wishes

Two studies included in the literature review explored predictors of refugees' wishes to return home. Findings showed that refugees who identified with the members of the receiving communities more and who perceived themselves as less discriminated, were also less likely to express wishes to return to their home country[32]. The same study showed that refugees with a higher level of education were more likely to wish to return, while refugees with better receiving community language proficiency were less likely to do so.

Additionally, the need for safety and level of current satisfaction with life were significant predictors of migrants' intentions to stay in the receiving country[33].

Taken together, these findings imply that not only economic, but socio-cultural and socio-psychological factors influence plans to stay in the receiving country and that relations to the receiving communities are influential in forming of refugees' wishes and intentions to return to their country of origin.

Conclusions

The literature review shows that research has identified a range of factors that facilitate or hinder socio-psychological integration of refugees and members of the receiving communities. The key relationships are set out here in Table 2:

[31] Di Saint Pierre, F., Martinovic, B., & De Vroome, T. (2015). Return Wishes of Refugees in the Netherlands: The Role of Integration, Host National Identification and Perceived Discrimination. *Journal of Ethnic & Migration Studies*, 41(11), pp. 1836–1857.

[32] Wilson, J., Ward, C., Fetvadjev, V. H., & Bethel, A. (2017). Measuring cultural competencies: The development and validation of a revised measure of sociocultural adaptation. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 48(10), pp. 1475–1506.

[33] Haase, A., Rohmann, A., & Hallmann, K. (2019). An ecological approach to psychological adjustment: A field survey among refugees in Germany. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 68, pp. 44–54.

[34] Cheah, W. H., Karamelic-Muratovic, A., & Matsuo, H. (2013). Ethnic-Group Strength Among Bosnian Refugees in St. Louis, Missouri, and Host Receptivity and Conformity Pressure. *Journal of Immigrant & Refugee Studies*, 11(4), pp. 401–415.)

Socio-psychological factors	Positive contribution to integration
Attitudes	Positive attitudes towards each other between refugees and members of the receiving communities facilitate integration. Such attitudes are often based on frequent and positive contact between both individuals and groups, and can be linked to support for migrants retaining their culture (acculturation).
Support for rights and asylum policies	Support for the rights of refugees and integrative asylum policies are related to other desirable outcomes, such as positive inter-group attitudes and proactive behavioural intentions . Such support can facilitate integration.
Behavioural intentions	Proactive behavioural intentions of members of the receiving communities towards refugees could ease the integration. Such demonstration of readiness to help and acceptance shown towards refugees can facilitate positive feelings and behaviours of refugees in the new community.
Contact	Both frequent and positive contact is strongly related to positive attitudes, support for the rights of refugees and positive behavioural intentions. Interventions aimed at reducing negative attitudes create opportunities for members of the two groups to experience positive contact over a longer period of time .
Perception of acculturation	Both members of the receiving communities and refugees see integration as desirable form of acculturation . This shows that both groups aim at preserving their culture , but also showing appreciation for the other culture.
Socio-psychological factors	Negative implications for integration
Social distance	Desire to maintain a greater social distance between the groups is related to negative attitudes of members of the receiving communities. High levels of social distance leads to social exclusion of refugees and prove as a barrier to integration.
Perception of inter-group threat	Perception of threat between groups is strongly related to negative attitudes. If one group feels a threat to its economic integrity, safety, culture and customs , it tends to reject the other group.
Perception of discrimination	The more refugees feel discriminated against, the more they are unwilling to maintain contact with the members of the receiving communities. Perception of discrimination therefore is an important barrier to integration as it could lead to separation of the groups, marginalization and isolation of the refugee group, with potential for conflict with the majority group.

Table 2: Socio-psychological factors related to integration of refugees and members of the receiving communities

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